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The average yield of Zhefu No. 7 was 6.1 t/ha in most areas, and 7 t/ha in a few areas. No significant difference in yield

was detected between Erjiufong and Zhefu No. 7 (Table 2). ■

Table 2. Yield performance^a of Zhefu No. 7 and check Erjiufong in regional tests in Zhejiang Province, China, 1990.

Site	Locations (no.)	Zhefu No. 7 yield (t/ha)	Erjiufong yield (t/ha)	Increase over check (%)
Hangzhou	13	5.97 ± 0.49	6.24 ± 0.49	-4.4
Fuyang	7	5.39 ± 0.40	5.28 ± 0.36	+2.0
Shaoxin	4	7.01 ± 0.27	6.78 ± 0.25	+3.3
Ningbo	22	6.56 ± 0.61	6.34 ± 0.59	+3.5
Linhai	10	5.37 ± 0.40	5.17 ± 0.34	+3.8

^aNo significant difference was detected at 0.05 level between Zhefu No. 7 and Erjiufong in any of the regional tests.

PNR162 (Renu), an early rice variety with superfine grain and multiple resistances

S. N. Chakrabarti, Genetics Division, Indian Agricultural Research Institute (IARI), New Delhi 110012, India

After several years in coordinated trials, PNR162 was recommended for release for West Bengal and Orissa states in India during the National Rice Workshop in 1989. The Government of Uttar

Pradesh released it for irrigated areas in Sep 1993. Its potential yield is 8 t/ha in northwestern India and about 9 t/ha in summer (boro) season in West Bengal (Table 1).

The variety has superfine grain, multiple resistances to pests, and other desirable characters (Table 2). It has become popular in many other parts of India because it can fit into various crop rotations. Its moderate cold tolerance makes it suitable in the high altitude

Table 1. Average grain yield (t/ha) of PNR162 in various trials, 1986-92.

Site	PNR162	IR36	Ratna	Pant 4	Saraju 52
Zone 3 ^a	3.5	2.9	-	-	-
Zone 4 ^a	3.9	3.6	-	-	-
Zone 6 ^a	4.8	4.3	-	-	-
Kerala ^b	3.3	2.1	3.0	-	-
Tamil Nadu ^b	5.6	5.2	4.4	-	-
Punjab ^b	4.9	4.2	4.7	-	-
Haryana ^b	7.9	7.3	7.1	-	-
Jammu and Kashmir ^a	5.3	2.7	-	-	-
Tripura ^a	4.5	3.6	-	-	-
Uttar Pradesh ^c	5.0	-	-	5.1	4.4

^aCoordinated trials, 1987 wet season. ^bCoordinated trials, 1986 wet season. ^cStation trials, 1991-92.

Table 2. Quality characters of PNR162.

Character	PNR162	Ratna (check)
Kernel length (mm)	7.0	6.6
Kernel breadth (mm)	2.0	2.1
Length-breadth ratio	3.5	3.2
Hulling (%)	79.0	75.0
Milling (%)	72.6	69.5
Head rice recovery (%)	56.0	55.0
Alkali value	4.0	6.0
Abdominal white	Absent	Absent

plains of Manipur, Arunachal Pradesh, and parts of Jammu and Kashmir.

In coordinated, state, and on-farm trials, the variety outperformed national and local checks (Table 1). Its nonshattering trait provides an advantage over Ratna, a popular variety of similar duration. PNR162 was developed from the cross Jaya Mutant (gamma radiation induced)/Basmati 370 through selection in two diverse environments. ■

Shanyou Wan 3, a medium-maturing, indica hybrid rice

He Shunwu, Hunan Hybrid Rice Research Center, Changsha 410125, Hunan, China

Minghui 63, an elite late-maturing rice restorer line, was used as the female parent in a cross with early-maturing rice restorer line 26 Zhaizao in 1984 autumn. The hybrid was planted that winter in Hainan, China. We treated the seeds harvested from the F₁ plants in 1985 with ⁶⁰Co gamma ray (D = 177 R/min, D = 2.2 × 10⁴ rad), planted the seeds, and conducted pedigree selection. In 1989, an early-maturing mutant plant was chosen and testcrossed with Zhenshan 97 A, with the testcross F₁ hybrid performing very well. This hybrid, named Shanyou Wan 3, was tested in 1990. Its restorer line was named Wan 3. The Crop Variety Release Committee of Hunan Province, China, approved Shanyou Wan 3 for commercial production in Jan 1994.

In 1990, Shanyou Wan 3 was tested in a multilocation trial and yielded an average 7.5 t/ha, 13.0% more than check hybrid Weiyou 64, and 10.3% more than check hybrid Shanyou Gui 33 (both significant at 1% level). It matured 5 d earlier than Shanyou Gui 33 and 4 d later than Weiyou 64. The average grain yield of Shanyou Gui 33 was 7.8 t/ha, 14.9% more than that of check Weiyou 64 in the 1991 Loudi Prefectural Rice Variety Regional Trial, Hunan Province (4 hybrids over 5 locations) (see table). In the 1991 All-China Indica Hybrid Rice Regional Trial, it ranked first in grain yield, with an average of 6.6 t/ha, and matured in 119 d. Compared with the check Shanyou Gui 33, its maturity duration, grain yield, and daily grain yield were 3.7 d longer, and 2.7% and 6.1% more, respectively. In 1992, Shanyou Wan 3 was cultivated for demonstration on 1,333 ha in several provinces and showed high-yielding ability. In 1993, it was planted on 44,667 ha.

Shanyou Wan 3 is 95-105 cm tall. It has stiff straw, good lodging tolerance, and adaptability to heavy fertilization. The panicles are 22-24 cm long with 120-130 spikelets per panicle. The seed setting rate is 80-85% and the 1,000-grain

Performance of Shanyou Wan 3. Loudi, Hunan Province, China. 1991.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets/panicle (no.)	Seed set (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Maturity duration (d)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Grain yield over check (%)	Daily grain yield (kg/ha)	Daily grain yield over check (%)
Shanyou Wan 3	102.0	23.8	125.2	71.4	28.7	116.2	7.76***	14.85	66.75	8.01
Weiyou 64 (check)	86.3	21.9	98.8	72.3	29.8	109.2	6.75	-	61.8	-

*** = significant at 1% level by Duncan's SSR test.

weight is about 28 g. It matures in 115-120 d, about 7-8 d earlier than Weiyou 64, and is grown as a late-cropped rice in various areas. Shanyou Wan 3 has strong resistance to blast and sheath blight. It is tolerant of high temperatures in the early growth stages and of coldness in the late stages. Its milling recovery rate is about 75%, and its eating quality is acceptable.

The hybrid has wide adaptability, yielding well at elevations from 200 to

1,150 m above sea level and in different soils.

Seed production is high. The restorer line, Wan 3, has about a 10-d flowering duration, large panicles, many spikelets per unit area, and heavy pollen load. If the flowering synchronization is good between the parents, more than 3 t of hybrid seed/ha can generally be produced.

For spring seed production of Shanyou Wan 3 in Changsha, Hunan Province, the restorer line is generally seeded in late March. The seeding interval between the CMS line (Zhenshan 97 A) and the restorer line is 5.0-5.3 leaves on the main culm or 20-25 d. For autumn seed production, the restorer line is usually sown in mid-June, with an 11-13 d seeding interval for the CMS line. ■

Promising rice blast-resistant cultivars

M. Saifulla, Plant Pathology Department, Agricultural College, University of Agricultural Sciences (UAS), Gandhi Krishi Vignyan Kendra (GKVK), Bangalore 560065, India; B. M. Devaiah, and N. M. Poornacha, Agricultural Research Station, Ponnampet 571216, S. Coorg, India; and A. Munjunath, Dry Farming Department, UAS

Rice blast is a serious disease in Coorg District of Karnataka, India. Resistance has been breaking down in some of the modern and local rice varieties, such as

Intan, BKB, PUB, Geerigesanna, and IET7191. We intensively screened rice germplasm for reaction to blast. Intan, which is grown on half of the rice area in the hill zone, was introduced in 1972 and lost its resistance to blast in 1983.

About 1,000 germplasm lines were screened for blast resistance under field conditions. Among the entries tested, NSN(H) 102-1988 was free from both leaf and neck blast during 1988 and 1992 kharif seasons. It also has desirable grain type, plant height, and duration and was selected for intensive screening with DWR4107 and Intan. These cultivars were screened in a

15-m² plot during 1990-92 kharif seasons. NSN(H) 102-1988 was free from both leaf and neck blast from 1990 to 1992.

Using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*, cultivar DWR4107 scored a maximum of 5 for both leaf and neck blast, and Intan scored a maximum of 5 for leaf blast and 9 for neck blast over the 5-yr study. NSN(H) 102-1988 was free from both leaf and neck blast disease and performed well in yield trials during 1990-92 kharif seasons. It had a mean yield of 2.7 t/ha compared with 2.5 t/ha for DWR4107 and 1.9 t/ha for Intan (see table). ■

Performance of NSN(H) 102-1988 at Ponnampet, S. Coorg, India. 1988-92.

Cultivar	Leaf blast ^a (score)					Neck blast ^a (score)					Yield (t/ha)			
	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1990	1991	1992	Mean
NSN(H) 102-1988	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.6	4.0	1.9	2.7
DWR4107	3	-	-	0	5	5	-	-	0	5	2.2	4.3	0.8	2.5
Intan	7	9	5	5	5	5	-	5	9	9	1.6	3.3	0.8	1.9

^aScored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed lowland

Luit, a short-duration rice variety for Assam, India

T. Ahmed and A. K. Pathak, Regional Agricultural Research Station (RARS), Assam Agricultural University (AAU), Titabar 785630, India

Floods may occur anytime from May to early September in Assam, India. Farmers need a short-duration rice variety that yields well and can be harvested before (Feb-May) and after (mid-Sep to early Dec) the floodwaters. Rice farmers in the flood-affected areas until recently grew early-maturing varieties—Culture 1,

Heera, and traditional types—that are low-yielding, have undesirable plant type, and are affected by low temperature at flowering when grown after the flood. A hybridization program was initiated in 1988 to develop short-duration photoperiod-insensitive rice varieties with high yield. Luit (IET13622) was